

Instructional Supervision Practices of Public Elementary School Heads: Basis for a Benchmarking Program

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Abstract. This study investigates the instructional supervision practices of public elementary school heads in the Sta. Cruz South district, Davao Del Sur, Philippines, with the aim of establishing a benchmarking program. Utilizing a researcher-made questionnaire, the study evaluates the supervision skills of 13 school heads through the perspectives of district supervisors, focusing on pre-observation, classroom observation, and post-observation practices. Data analysis involved statistical tools, particularly the mean, to determine the levels of supervision skills. The results indicated high levels of supervision skills across all stages, with pre-observation activities such as finalizing schedules and assisting teachers rated very high (mean = 4.29), classroom observation skills including curriculum integration and learner involvement also highly rated (mean = 4.28), and post-observation practices such as reflective discussions and identifying areas for improvement receiving very high ratings (mean = 4.32). These findings highlight the effectiveness of current supervision practices and provide a foundation for a benchmarking program to standardize and enhance instructional supervision across the district.

KEY WORDS

1. Instructional Supervision
2. Clinical Supervision
3. Benchmarking Program

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1. Introduction

One crucial aspect of educational management is instructional supervision, which can be defined as improving the teaching-learning process through cooperative activities and democratic relationships among those involved in teaching and learning. Instructional supervision is essential for achieving an effective education system (Oyewole Ehinola, 2019). It primarily focuses on student learning in the classroom and involves collaborative efforts aimed at improving the teaching and learning process. There is evidence to suggest that a single teacher can significantly impact student achievement, even if the school does not. To ensure academic success for all students, we believe that high-quality instruction should be the standard rather than the exception within schools and across districts. This means that teachers need to establish a shared approach to instruction and effectively utilize a common set of teaching strategies that are highly likely to improve student achievement (Brophy Good, 2019). The landscape of education has been dramatically transformed by digital and technological advancements in the twenty-first century. The world has transitioned from the first industrial revolution in

the eighteenth century to the fourth industrial revolution, which focuses on the use of artificial intelligence, big data, and the Internet of Things. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the move towards the fifth industrial revolution, where there is an emphasis on the "re-connection of innovation to flourishing humanity" (5th Element Group, PBC cited in Gauri, 2019) and "deep, multi-level cooperation between people and machine" (Regensys Business School, 2020). The role of educational institutions has become more crucial than ever considering these developments. Today, educational institutions are expected to produce graduates who possess twenty-first-century skills, which include core competencies such as collaboration, critical thinking, digital literacy, and problem-solving. Therefore, educational institutions need to create an academic environment that fosters the development of these competencies in students. This involves not only improving physical and information technology infrastructure but also enhancing the competencies of the workforce, particularly the teachers. Teachers are among the most significant factors that affect student outcomes. Thus, to improve the achievement of students, it is essential to enhance the competence of teachers, and one significant mechanism for achieving this is through an instructional supervision program (Maisyaroh et al., 2018). On the other hand, a principal or supervisor focuses on human relations, making curriculum decisions, implementing instructional strategies, conducting staff development and orientations, addressing budget concerns, and handling assessment and evaluation. Wiles and Bondi (2002) state that "Supervision in schools is seen as a general leadership function that coordinates and manages activities related to learning." School administrators must have a vision and be willing to facilitate changes within the schools they are responsible for. In other words, supervisory activities encompass various aspects of human operations

such as the social, physical, and psychological elements. It's important to note that some educators are hesitant to use the term "supervision" because they incorrectly link it to a hierarchical relationship based on an industrial model of schooling (Stoller, 2008). On the contrary, Edward C. Elliot, an early 20th-century educator as cited by Cooper (2004), described supervision in schools as being closely related to the democratic motive of American education. He clearly distinguished centralization of administrative power, which he said stifled creativity and individuality in school, from decentralization, expertise, cooperation, and supervisory dimensions as models of collaborations in any administration destined to bear enough fruit. It is with and in this traditional democratic approach and understanding of supervision in education and its long-standing respect for creativity, cooperation, decentralization, and individual difference that we now set out to offer the meaning of Clinical Supervision and its aspects. According to Delworth (2011), instructional supervision is based on a positive relationship between supervisors and supervisees. This relationship should focus on promoting the client's well-being and the supervisee's professional development. Individuals in roles such as school head, coach, consultant, mentor, and evaluator should support, encourage, and educate staff members. They should also address clients' various educational, interpersonal, physical, and spiritual issues. Ultimately, adequate clinical supervision ensures that clients receive competent care. Supervision also helps counselors improve their skills, treatment outcomes, client retention, and staff satisfaction. Additionally, clinical supervisors act as a bridge between administrative and clinical staff. In the Division of Davao Del Sur, particularly in Sta. Cruz South District, instructional supervision is a prevalent problem. Even though school heads have administered clinical supervision, the process is problematic because they have not been able to solve the instructional

problems faced by the teachers. Due to this, the researcher is conducting a study to address this problem in the hope of identifying and resolving the underlying factors.

1.1. *Review of Related Literature—*

1.1.1. *Instructional Supervision—*Clinical supervision is crucial for bridging classroom learning with real-world practice, particularly in fields like substance abuse treatment (Falvey, 2010). It aims to enhance the teaching and learning process through cooperative activities and democratic relationships among educators (Archibong, 2018). Supervisors and teachers should establish good rapport and clear objectives before observations (Hopkins Moore, 2022; Denzin, 2005). Supervision involves a complex process of collaboration to enhance educational quality (Beach Reinhartz, 2018; Moswela, 2020). Effective pre-observation conferences, where goals and methods are discussed, are key to improving instructional supervision (Gordon, 2000; Pajak, 2000; Waite, 2003).

1.1.2. *Classroom Observation—*Classroom observation involves evaluating teaching methods and interactions to improve instructional quality (Wainryb, 2005). It helps teachers identify strengths and weaknesses and adapt their teaching methods accordingly (Smyth, 2008; Durkin, 2008). Effective observation includes setting clear goals, systematic data collection, and constructive feedback (Tuncay, 2020; Vossoughi, 2020). Observations can be formal or informal and are essential for professional development (Creswell, 2012; Borj, 2007).

1.1.3. *Post-Observation Conference—*Post-observation conferences are critical for discussing and reflecting on the collected data to enhance instructional practices (Smyth, 2013; Chamberlin, 2000). They should be collaborative, focusing on both strengths and areas for improvement (Copland, 2012). Effective conferences lead to tangible changes in teaching

practices and greater confidence in implementing feedback (Blumberg, 2010; Brandt, 2008). These discussions are crucial for continuous teacher development and improved educational outcomes (Glatthorn, 2007; Glickman, 2006).

1.2. *Synthesis—*The review of related literature from different authors presents various ideas about clinical supervision. Some authors share similar views on clinical supervision, while others have slightly different perspectives. Some suggest that clinical supervision is an instructional style used by school managers to enhance classroom instruction. Conversely, some argue that clinical supervision is an ongoing, lengthy process that may involve the teacher, school head, and supervisor working together to address challenges. If the teacher and school head are unable to devise a strategy to solve a problem, it may be beneficial to involve the supervisor to observe how the school head provides technical assistance to the teacher.

1.3. *Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—*This study is grounded on the theory of Dewar and Walker (1999) who expressed that the mentor needs to provide an appropriate learning environment, relevant resources, and the desirable level of structured support and guidance to promote professional growth and development. The individual support worker must interact with the mentor in a manner that suggests they are prepared to learn. They must demonstrate personal motivation and an attitude that is open to acquiring new knowledge. Workplace learning, through structured mentorship, coaching through clinical supervision. Clinical supervision as instruction supervision has the following phases: pre-observation, observation, analysis and strategy, post-observation conference, and post-observation analysis. This type of supervision needs to be recognized by organizations as an important future strategy in bridging the theory-to-practice gap, motivating support workers, and promoting the application of knowledge to practice. This is supported by

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Variables of the Study.

Santos and Stuart (2003) who expressed that even though organizations invest millions of pounds in training programs they often devote little attention to evaluating the effectiveness of training. There has been a recent cultural shift in continuous professional development away from classroom-based teaching to interactive workplace learning through good mentorship. Training should not be confined to the classroom and should include practical as well as theoretical elements. Good supervision should promote the support worker’s accountability and

provide feedback in a supportive environment. Supervision ensures the support worker’s competence and provides pastoral support (Nancarrow Mackey, 2005). The schematic diagram of this study illustrates the model used by the research in conducting it. In this study, the researcher uses the Input-Process-Output model. The input is clinical supervision as a type of classroom observation with the following indicators: pre-observation, classroom observation, analysis and strategy, post-observation, and post-observation analysis.

1.4. *Statement of the Problem*—This study determined the level of school head instructional supervision skills in how they conduct

clinical supervision in the classroom. Eventually, it will produce a benchmarking program that will serve as its output.

- (1) What is the level of the instructional supervision skills of the public elementary school heads as perceived by district supervisors in terms of:
 - (1) Pre-Observation Stage,
 - (2) Classroom Observation Stage,
 - (3) Post Observation Stage?
- (2) Based on the study’s findings, what benchmarking program can be proposed?

1.5. *Null Hypothesis*—Since the significance of the difference and the significance of the relationship are not to be explored, this study is hypothesis-free. This study will be of great help to the following identified beneficiaries of this study. DepEd Officials. The Department of Education should monitor the implementation of clinical supervision as an approach to

strengthening classroom instruction. Monitoring this program should produce recommendations on how to effectively apply clinical supervision in the classroom, which would be appreciated by the teachers, the school head, and even the supervisors. School Heads. The school heads should have deep knowledge and skills in applying clinical supervision in the classroom so that classroom observation is effective and

addresses the academic problem in instruction. Teachers. Teachers should understand that classroom observation is done to improve instruction. It should not be taken negatively as its purpose is to extend technical assistance to deliver quality education to the learners. They should understand that the school heads have an instructional

responsibility in school. These responsibilities are discharged strategically to achieve the vision of the Department of Education. Future Researchers. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies about instructional supervision.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed a non-experimental descriptive survey research design to investigate the research problem. It is descriptive because the data are presented in quantitative descriptions in the “Instructional Supervision Skills of Public Elementary School Heads: Basis for a Benchmarking Program”. According to Good (2005), this research method shows merely a description of tasks presenting the conditions regarding the nature of the group of persons or class of events that involved the procedure of analysis, classi-

fication, and measurement. It involves varied information regarding the current or present condition (Deauna, 2005).

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted on all public elementary schools in the division of Davao Del Sur, particularly in Sta. Cruz South district. The respondents will be the 13 school heads. A universal sampling procedure will be used in this study, considering the minimal number of respondents. The research respondents will be rated by their district supervisor on how they conduct clinical supervision.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study utilized the researcher-made questionnaire which focuses on the supervisory skills of school heads in conducting clinical supervision. The ques-

tionnaire will be pilot tested in a school that is not a respondent to this study using cron bach alpha to test its validity and reliability. To determine the level of supervisory skills of school heads, the following continuum will be used.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—At the outset of the data-gathering procedure, the researcher will draft a letter seeking permission

for this research study to be conducted and send it to Dr. Lorenzo Mendoza, CESO V, the Schools Division Superintendent in the Davao

Distribution of Respondents

School	Number of School Heads
Santa Cruz Central ES	1
Patulangon ES	1
Loay Elementary School	1
Agripina Elementary School	1
Tuban Elementary School	1
Ciriaco Gudoy Elementary School	1
Anastancio G. Canda Elementary School	1
Tagabuli Elementary School	1
Sinuron Elementary School	1
Melilla Elementary School	1
Saliducon Elementary School	1
Matutungan Elementary School	1
Apolinar Franco Elementary School	1
Total	13

Del Sur division, and to the Elementary School Principals of the elementary schools in Sta. Cruz North and South district. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the DepEd Schools Division Superintendent and principals concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire, which the experts validated and pilot-tested using cron back alpha. After permission has been granted for this study to be conducted in the research locale and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators and pilot tested, the

researchers will launch the questionnaire into the field and retrieve it from the respondents personally after a few days. Finally, the raw scores were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation, after which the researcher analyzed and interpreted the results.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—In this study, we will use statistical tools for analyzing and interpreting the responses. We will use the mean to determine the level of instructional supervision skills of school heads in the Sta. Cruz South district.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented a discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Level of the instructional supervision skills of the public elementary school heads as perceived by district supervisors in terms of pre-observation, Level of the instructional supervision skills of the public elementary school heads as perceived by district supervisors in terms of classroom observation, Level of the instructional supervision skills of the public elementary school heads as perceived by district supervisors in terms of post-observation, and significant relationship between instructional supervision practices of public elementary school heads and benchmarking program.

3.1. *Level of the instructional supervision skills of the public elementary school heads as perceived by district supervisors in terms of pre-observation*—Table 1 shows the level of

instructional supervision skills of the public elementary school heads as perceived by district supervisors in terms of pre-observation. In this discussion, the following responses yielded by

Interval	Level	Criteria
4.20 – 5.0	VERY HIGH	When the supervisory skills of school heads in the conduct of clinical supervision during instruction observation is always manifested
2.40 – 3.19	HIGH	When the supervisory skills of school heads in the conduct of clinical supervision during instruction observation is oftentimes manifested
1.60 – 2.39	MODERATE	When the supervisory skills of school heads in the conduct of clinical supervision during instruction observation is manifested sometimes only
0.80 – 1.59	LOW	When the supervisory skills of school heads in the conduct of clinical supervision during instruction observation is seldom manifested
0 – 0.79	VERY LOW	When the supervisory skills of school heads in the conduct of clinical supervision during instruction observation is never manifested

the respondents were given for comprehensive emphasis: Finalized schedule for the classroom observation with a rating of 4.45 or very high, Assisted teacher in identifying competencies to be taught with a rating of 4.33 or very high, Set conference with the teacher with a rating of 4.30 or very high, Guided teacher on how the lesson would be unfolded with a rating of 4.28 or high, and Facilitated the discussion on the activities to be undertaken during the observation process with a rating of 4.10 or high. It received an overall mean rating of 4.29 or high. This meant that school heads oftentimes observed classes in order to provide technical assistance even in the pre-observation process.”

Table 1: Level of Instructional Supervision Skills of Public Elementary School Heads

Item	Description	Mean	Description
a.	Sets a conference with the teacher	4.30	Very High
b.	Assists teacher in identifying competencies to be taught	4.33	Very High
c.	Guides teacher on how the lesson will be unfolded	4.28	High
d.	Facilitates the discussion on the activities to be undertaken during the observation process	4.10	High
e.	Finalizes schedule for the classroom observation	4.45	Very High
Overall		4.29	High

This finding supports Benjamin’s (2020) argument that the pre-observation stage of the instructional supervision process should address the specific needs of the teachers being supervised. By customizing supervisory approaches to individual needs, there is great potential to improve motivation and commitment at work. Common approaches to instructional supervision include clinical supervision, collegial supervision, inquiry-based supervision,

self-directive supervision, and informal supervision. Hopkins and Moore (2022) stress the importance of building a strong rapport and laying the groundwork for the observation process during the pre-observation stage for both the supervisor and teacher. They outline the goals of the observation, the methods for collecting data, and how the data will be used.

3.2. *Level of the instructional supervision skills of the public elementary school heads as perceived by district supervisors in terms of Classroom observation*—Table 2 presents the level of instructional supervision skills of the public elementary school heads as perceived by district supervisors in terms of classroom

observation. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Anchors lesson in the Curriculum Guide with a rating of 4.45 or very high, Involves the learners in the teaching-learning process with a rating of 4.44 or very high, Gives authentic evaluation with a rating of 4.26 or high, Selects appropriate strategies with a rating of 4.19 or high, and Processes responses of the learners with a rating of 4.09 or high. It got an overall rating of 4.28 or high. This also means that school heads oftentimes conduct classroom observation as the basis for their technical assistance in classroom instruction,

Table 2: Level of Instructional Supervision Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in Terms of Classroom Observation

Item	Description	Mean	Description
a.	Anchors lesson in the Curriculum Guide	4.45	Very High
b.	Selects appropriate strategies	4.19	High
c.	Involves the learners in the teaching-learning process	4.44	Very High
d.	Processes responses of the learners	4.09	High
e.	Gives authentic evaluation	4.26	High
Overall		4.28	High

According to Kane (2012), it is important for classroom observations to improve teaching by having teachers clearly identify their strengths and weaknesses and acknowledge areas for improvement in their knowledge and skills. However, relying only on self-assessment may not be enough and could be problematic. Research shows a weak correlation between teachers' self-assessments and their actual teaching practices. Additionally, due to the

complexity and busyness of classrooms, teachers may miss much of what happens during teaching. Jensen (2014) discovered that improving teacher effectiveness has a more significant influence on student performance than any other school program or policy. Numerous studies similarly emphasize the crucial role of enhancing teacher effectiveness in improving educational outcomes. While student achievement data can indicate teacher effectiveness, it

provides limited insight into the specific practices that lead to these outcomes and how teachers can further improve their methods to boost student achievement.

3.3. *Level of the instructional supervision skills of the public elementary school heads as perceived by district supervisors in terms of post-observation*—Table 3 presented the level of instructional supervision skills of the public elementary school heads as perceived by district supervisors in terms of post-observation. In this discussion, the following responses yielded by the respondents were given for comprehensive emphasis: Discussed what went well and what did not go well during the teaching-learning process with a rating of 4.52 or very high, Led the teacher to discover his/her weak points with a rating of 4.47 or very high, Set post-conference with the teacher with a rating of 4.38 or very

high, Set schedule for another classroom observation with a rating of 4.27 or high, and Provided technical assistance with a rating of 4.00 or high. It obtained an overall rating of 4.32 or very high. This also meant that school heads always conducted post-conferences after their classroom observation to process the things they observed during the classroom observation and to provide technical assistance to make the teaching-learning process more productive and meaningful. This finding aligns with McGreal’s (2012) concept that the Observation/Feedback approach is rooted in teacher evaluation literature, clinical supervision, cognitive processes, and peer coaching. Typically, an observation guide or focusing instrument is used to narrow the scope of the observation. A pre-conference may be conducted to gather more information before the actual observation.

Table 3: Level of Instructional Supervision Skills of Public Elementary School Heads in Terms of Post-Observation

Item	Description	Mean	Description
a.	Sets post conference with the teacher	4.38	Very High
b.	Discusses what went well and what did not go well during the teaching-learning process	4.52	Very High
c.	Leads the teacher to discover his/her weak points	4.47	Very High
d.	Provides technical assistance	4.00	High
e.	Sets schedule for another classroom observation	4.27	High
Overall		4.32	Very High

Tuncay (2020) explains that observation in language classrooms involves a systematic and purposeful examination of teaching and learning events. Vossoughi (2020) adds that observations are conducted to gather and record information for both immediate formative assess-

ment and later summative assessment. After the observations, post-observation conferences take place, during which the trainer shares insights and evaluations regarding the trainee’s teaching practice.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter summarizes the findings, conclusions, and recommendations drawn by the researcher after analyzing and interpreting the findings. This study determined the level of school head instructional supervision skills in conducting clinical supervision in the classroom. Eventually, it will produce a benchmarking program that will serve as its output. This study will employ a non-experimental descriptive survey research design to investigate the research problem. It is descriptive because the data are presented in quantitative descriptions in the “Instructional Supervision Practices of Public Elementary School Heads: Basis for a Benchmarking Program.” According to Good (2005), this research method shows merely a description of tasks presenting the conditions regarding the nature of the group of persons or class of events that involved the procedure of analysis, classification, and measurement. It involves varied information regarding the current or present condition (Deauna, 2005). This research will be carried out in all public secondary schools within the division of Davao del Sur, specifically in the Sta. Cruz South District. The study involves 32 school heads as respondents. Due to the small number of respondents, a universal sampling procedure will be utilized. The research respondents will be evaluated by their district supervisor based on their performance in conducting clinical supervision. This revealed that school heads have good instructional supervision practices as a basis for their provision of technical assistance to teachers. This also means that part of their instructional supervision practices is regular classroom observation to single out things in the instructional process where the teacher needs to improve further by giving intensified technical assistance.

4.1. *Conclusions*—Based on the collective findings of this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The instructional supervision practices of the public elementary school heads in terms of pre-observation are High, Classroom observation is High, and Post-Observation is Very High.

4.2. *Recommendations*—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that DepEd develop short-term courses for school heads to serve as refresher courses. The contents of these courses

are derived from the domains in the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads, focusing on instructional supervision. The school heads should strengthen their professional development by attending graduate or postgraduate studies. Attending trainings and other forms of learning and development is also encouraged, as this will help them develop their skills in school-based management, particularly in instructional supervision. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the instructional supervision practices of school heads in relation to other variables in the school context will be conducted.

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